

NPOWER
BALANCING N & P FLOWS

D.7.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

Authors: Rural Loop, Strane Innovation, Water Europe

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Authors	Fernando Ezequiel Lerner (LOOP), Chiara Lacroix (STRANE), Ana De León (WE)
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The NPower Project

NPower aims to reduce nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions and rebalance nutrient flows across key sectors in Europe. By advancing nutrient recovery technologies, best management practices (BMPs), and governance measures, the project will contribute to more efficient and circular nutrient use, minimising environmental impact while supporting agricultural and industrial sustainability.

Running for four years from January 2025, NPower will:

- Develop an innovative N/P budgeting software model to analyse and optimise nutrient flows across five key emitting sectors.
- Demonstrate 6 nutrient recovery technologies (RT) to produce sustainable fertilisers.
- Promote 20 best management practices to improve nutrient efficiency and reduce emissions.
- Design and implement governance measures to support effective nutrient management policies at local, regional, and EU levels.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer across four Regional Clusters (RCs) in Spain, Belgium, Finland, and Ireland to ensure EU-wide applicability.

Spain will serve as the main demonstration site, implementing recovery technologies, while the other RCs will assess their applicability and potential replication in their respective contexts. Led by a consortium of 25 partners from across Europe, NPower integrates expertise from research, industry, and policy, covering the entire N/P value chain. This collaboration will provide practical, scalable solutions to optimise nutrient cycles and support the EU's sustainability goals.

Consortium Members

Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country
COORDINATOR	CETENMA	ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DE LA ENERGIA Y DEL MEDIO AMBIENTE DE LA REGION DE MURCIA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	CTQ	FUNDACION CENTRO GALLEGO DE INVESTIGACIONES DEL AGUA	SPAIN
ASSOCIATED ENTITY	HGA	HIDROGEA GESTION INTEGRAL DE AGUAS DE MURCIA SOCIEDAD ANONIMA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	CSIC	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	IMIDA	INSTITUTO MURCIANO DE INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO AGRARIO Y MEDIOAMBIENTAL (IMIDA)	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	LUKE	LUONNONVARAKESKUS	FINLAND
BENEFICIARY	UPCT	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE CARTAGENA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	UGENT	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	BELGIUM
BENEFICIARY	MTU	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	IRELAND
BENEFICIARY	UCD	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	IRELAND
BENEFICIARY	LMB	LAMBERT EUROPA, SL	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	JISAP	JUAN JIMENEZ GARCIA SAU	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	DAB	DAB BIOTECNOLOGIA SL	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	PBT	PROBELTE SA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	KVC	SENIOR EUROPA SOCIEDAD LIMITADA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	FMRM	FEDERACION DE MUNICIPIOS DE LA REGION DE MURCIA	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	FECOAM	FEDERACION DE COOPERATIVAS AGRARIAS DE MURCIA S COOP	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	BOER	BOERENBOND PROJECTEN	BELGIUM
BENEFICIARY	WE	WATER EUROPE	BELGIUM
BENEFICIARY	IBF	IRISH BIOECONOMY FOUNDATION	IRELAND
BENEFICIARY	STRANE	STRANE INNOVATION	FRANCE
BENEFICIARY	LOOP	CERTIFIED CLIMATE ACTIONS	SPAIN
BENEFICIARY	MTK	MTK POHJOIS-SUOMI RY	FINLAND
BENEFICIARY	CARM	REGION DE MURCIA	SPAIN
ASSOCIATED PARTNER	ZHAW	ZURCHER HOCHSCHULE FUR ANGEWANDTE WISSENSCHAFTEN	SWITZERLAND

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BMP	Best Management Practice
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DNSH	Do Not Significant Harm
FTO	Freedom-To-Operate
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
N	Nitrogen
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
P	Phosphorus
PA	Practice Abstract
RF	Recovered Fertilizers
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WIE	Water Innovation Europe
WKE	Water Knowledge Europe
WP	Work Package
WPE	Water Projects Europe

1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan for the NPower project (Grant Agreement 101181873), co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme. NPower aims to deliver demonstrated and qualified (TRL8) solutions to limit Nitrogen and Phosphorus (N/P) emissions across five key emitting sectors, through circular approaches and regionally adapted strategies. The project involves 25 partners from 6 European countries, including 4 Regional Clusters (Spain, Belgium, Finland, Ireland) that act as hubs of co-creation and local action.

The DEC Plan has been designed to ensure strategic and effective engagement with target audiences, tailored to their specific interests, knowledge needs and levels of involvement. It defines the guiding communication principles and goals, the key messages per target audience, the selected channels, content formats and timing. Moreover, it explains how the circular communication model (Recover, Recycle, Redistribute, Return) will be applied to maximise outreach and impact.

The document also sets out the dissemination strategy, formats, a KPI-based monitoring approach either for communication and dissemination efforts, as well as the synergies with other initiatives and platforms that will be carried out during the project duration.

Moreover, the DEC Plan also includes the preliminary exploitation strategy led by Strane Innovation, which will be updated as the project progresses.

This deliverable will be periodically revised (M18, M36, M48) to adjust the strategy and contents to the evolving needs, milestones, and outcomes of NPower.

2. Introduction

This document outlines the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the NPower project. Rural Loop is responsible for leading and coordinating the DEC strategy across the consortium, with the active involvement of all partners. Strane Innovation leads the exploitation-related tasks, which are developed in parallel and aligned with communication and dissemination actions.

NPower aims to rebalance Nitrogen and Phosphorus flows by delivering circular solutions tailored to five key emitting sectors: agriculture, water/waste management, industry, energy and transport, and other primary sectors. These solutions are being co-created and demonstrated through four Regional Clusters located in Spain, Belgium, Finland, and Ireland. Each cluster reflects different regional realities and levels of N/P impact, ensuring the project's outcomes are relevant and scalable across Europe.

NPower combines recovery technologies, best management practices (BMPs), and governance tools to reduce emissions and regenerate circular nutrient cycles. The project takes place in a context of growing concern about nutrient-related pollution and resource efficiency across the EU, which are directly linked with EU policy goals such as the Green Deal, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

In this context, the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan has been designed to support stakeholder engagement, promote the project's outcomes, and maximise impact through clear, engaging, and inclusive messaging. This document starts from an analysis of the different target audiences, which serves as the foundation for a well-structured and goal-driven DEC strategy. It then details the channels, roles, visual identity, and activities that will support NPower's visibility and long-term value.

In line with NPower's overarching goal of fostering a circular economy of nutrients, the communication strategy itself is designed to follow the same principles of circularity. Inspired by the regenerative logic applied to nutrient flows, this approach treats information not as a one-off message, but as a resource that can be recovered, recycled, and redistributed across platforms and audiences. This circular communication model ensures that each piece of content is adapted, reused, and reinforced over time, maximising its reach and relevance while supporting continuous engagement and knowledge transfer.

3. Target Audiences

In NPower, the success and adoption of results depend on effective engagement with carefully defined target audiences across sectors and governance levels. The project identifies specific audience groups aligned with its objectives of dissemination (D), communication (C), and exploitation (E).

NPower's efforts are centred around five key emitting sectors:

- S1. Agriculture
- S2. Other Primary Sectors (e.g., aquaculture, forestry, mining)
- S3. Water/Waste Management
- S4. Energy and Transport
- S5. Industrial Sectors

Within and across these sectors, NPower has identified the following target audiences, each with distinct motivations and roles in reducing N/P emissions and enabling circular nutrient solutions. These groups will be addressed through tailored messages adapted to their technical capacity, interest, and level of influence.

Table 1. Targeted audiences

ID	Target Audience	Scope	Objective to Reach	Key Messages
1	Practitioners (e.g. agriculture, aquaculture, water management, bioenergy)	D, C, E	Adoption of systemic and multi-actor transition pathways. Behavioural change to reduce N/P emissions and promote intersectoral cooperation.	Importance of reducing N/P emissions; role of practitioners in solutions; benefits of NPower solutions.
2	Sectorial organisations and Regional Clusters	D, C, E	Informed about effective, demonstrated solutions against N/P imbalance that promote industrial synergies.	Key role in achieving coordinated efforts to reduce N/P pollution.
3	Research and academia (including sciences and SSH)	D, C	Demonstrated knowledge on environmental, societal and economic benefits of N/P technologies, BMPs, governance.	Characteristics and performance of NPower outputs; new research avenues opened by the project.
4	Regulatory entities and public administrations (EU,	D, C	Deeper understanding of N/P emission landscape; access to	Barriers, opportunities and incentives for implementing N/P-

ID	Target Audience	Scope	Objective to Reach	Key Messages
	national, regional, municipal)		holistic solutions to reduce N/P emissions.	reducing actions across sectors and governance levels.
5	Civil society organisations (e.g. environmental NGOs, consumer associations)	D, C	Improved coordination between civil society, industry needs and public policy.	Emphasis on public-funded, multi-actor efforts to enhance environmental and social well-being.

By aligning the DEC strategies with these target audiences, NPower ensures that content development, media outreach, and stakeholder collaboration remain focused and impactful throughout the project lifecycle. This approach helps the project's outreach efforts resonate more deeply, fostering engagement, knowledge exchange, and meaningful interactions.

4. Communication

4.1 Communication Strategy & Approach

NPower's communication strategy is driven by the Circular Communication Model, inspired by the same logic the project applies to nutrient flows. In this model, communication is not linear but cyclical, with each piece of content or message being repurposed, re-shared, and adapted for different uses, platforms, and audiences.

Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flow through ecosystems, but when they fail to reach their intended destination, they cause pollution or go to waste. Communication works in much the same way: messages, like nutrients, must be used and directed efficiently and appropriately to maximise their impact.

- Recover: Identify relevant knowledge and project outputs.
- Recycle: Transform these into formats tailored to each audience. A podcast becomes a blog article, a video becomes short clips, a research report becomes a LinkedIn carousel.
- Redistribute: Share them across appropriate channels – LinkedIn, YouTube, events, newsletters.
- Return: Monitor and gather feedback through analytics and interaction metrics to refine future communication.

Figure 1. Circular communication strategy overview

This approach ensures that project content flows like the circular economy of nutrients NPower is promoting.

4.2 Communication Goals:

- Raise awareness of nutrient imbalances and circular economy solutions.
- Ensure high visibility of project outcomes among target audiences.
- Promote EU-level and regional relevance of the developed solutions and governance tools.
- Support replication and adoption through engaging content.

4.3 Communication Channels and Content Formats

Each communication channel used in NPower has been selected based on its ability to reach specific audiences, support particular content formats, and amplify engagement.

Project Website

The NPower website – www.npower.es – is the project's main digital anchor point. It provides background on project mission and context, structure and developments, and information about partners involved. The website will be continuously updated as the project develops and outreach its outcomes. It will host blog articles, multimedia, events, and serves as a gateway to other communication tools.

Target audience: Broad (researchers, industry, public authorities, policy makers, NGOs, general public).

Figure 2. NPower webpage overview

“Powie” Chatbot

Aligned with the ongoing AI revolution and the growing accessibility of digital tools, NPower will introduce “Powie” — the project’s friendly mascot and interactive assistant. Embedded within the website, Powie will serve as an engaging, approachable resource to answer questions related to the project and its broader context.

Target audience: General public, students, practitioners, and stakeholders seeking quick, accessible information (e.g. researchers, industry, NGOs, and public authorities).

Figure 3. “Powie” IA assistant’s first impression

Newsletter

The “NPowered News” newsletter will be issued quarterly to summarise key project updates including blog articles, videos, event coverage, partner activities, and newly published resources. It will serve as a key tool to maintain an ongoing connection with stakeholders and expand awareness of NPower’s progress.

The newsletter will be managed through the Mailchimp platform and distributed via email to a growing list of subscribers. A dedicated subscription link will be available on the NPower website to facilitate sign-up and ensure GDPR-compliant data management. Content will be concise, visually engaging, and structured for quick reading — complemented by previews and links to full materials.

Target audience: Stakeholders subscribed to updates, including researchers, policy makers, practitioners.

Figure 4. Newsletter overview

LinkedIn page

LinkedIn will serve as NPower’s primary and most dynamic social media channel for engaging with the EU research and innovation ecosystem. It will feature a wide range of content including project updates, infographics, partner highlights, event coverage, and quotes from experts. The platform will also host and amplify multimedia outputs such as podcasts, short videos, and Explained-in-a-Minute content. In addition, it will be an outlet for the communication of Practice Abstracts and other project materials as they become available.

Target audience: Researchers, innovation networks, industry stakeholders, policy makers, and EU-level initiatives.

Figure 5. NPower LinkedIn profile overview

Podcast

The “NPowered Talks” podcast will be structured into annual seasons, featuring interviews and narratives that explore nutrient challenges, and the voices of stakeholders across Europe. Episodes will be creatively sound-edited to offer a dynamic listening experience, combining informative content with an engaging, accessible tone. This format allows for the construction of meaningful dialogues and storytelling around the project, making technical and policy-related topics more relatable. As a widely consumed medium across audience types, the podcast offers a versatile communication channel that supports both awareness-raising and deeper engagement.

Target audience: General public, practitioners, environmental communicators, researchers, and policy influencers.

Figure 6. NPower podcast “NPowered talks” cover image

YouTube

YouTube will host all of NPower’s video content, including podcast episodes, and the “Explained in a Minute” series. This platform enables NPower to enhance its messaging through dynamic visual content, aligning with contemporary consumption habits.

With over 2.5 billion monthly active users as of 2024, YouTube stands as the second most-used social media platform globally, just behind Facebook. Notably, 91.8% of internet users worldwide watch digital videos each week, highlighting the platform's extensive reach.

Target audience: General public, educators, researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in environmental sustainability and nutrient management.

Figure 7. Youtube channel overview

Explained-in-a-Minute Videos

This series will consist of short, creatively produced videos designed to explain — in just one minute or so— the core ideas behind the project and the broader nutrient challenge it addresses. These videos will combine strong visual storytelling with accessible language to explore concepts such as what nitrogen and phosphorus are, why their excess harms ecosystems, and how circular solutions can make a difference.

Each video will be carefully scripted, narrated, and edited to deliver clear, memorable messages about transversal topics like eutrophication, biodiversity loss, nutrient economics, or the vision of a circular nutrient economy. With their creative and cohesive format, these videos are meant not only to inform but also to spark curiosity and raise awareness among a wide, non-specialist audience.

Target audience: General public, educators, media channels, and stakeholders looking for accessible, science-based insights.

Blog

This section will be fully integrated into the NPower website, publishing articles throughout the project's duration. The blog will include content derived from podcasts, Practice Abstracts, technological updates, interviews with partners, and highlights from events.

It will serve as a dynamic and evolving space to understand the full arc of the project's development — step by step. From early insights and activities to final outcomes, the blog will offer accessible narratives that reflect the project's progress, challenges, and milestones.

Target audience: General public, experts, project partners, and stakeholders interested in following the project's evolution in a more narrative and accessible format.

Figure 8. NPower blog overview

Practice Abstracts

Practice Abstracts (PAs) are a core tool for knowledge transfer in Horizon Europe projects, designed to translate technical findings into actionable guidance for practitioners. These documents will highlight outcomes from pilots, technologies, best management practices (BMPs), governance tools, and stakeholder feedback.

Practice Abstracts will include a short title, problem description, solution overview, and expected benefits, as well as be accessible either in English and Spanish, in alignment with the project's bilingual approach.

PAs will be published using the EIP-AGRI format and uploaded to relevant EU platforms.

Rural Loop will coordinate the formatting and communication of these abstracts across project channels.

Target audience: Farmers and land managers, technical advisors, local authorities, practitioners in water and waste management, and other sectoral actors seeking practical and evidence-based guidance.

4.4 Monitoring of Communication Actions

Throughout the project, a set of key indicators will be regularly monitored to ensure that the consortium remains responsive to emerging needs and maximises the impact of its communication and dissemination efforts. The following table outlines the main KPIs regarding communication actions, which will be reviewed on M22, M36, and M48.

Table 2. KPIs for Communication Actions

Channel	KPI	Target	M22	M36	M48
Website	Unique visits	5000			
Blog	Posts	30			
Newsletter	Newsletter subscribers	400			
LinkedIn	Total followers	1,200			
Practice Abstracts	Deliveries	40			

4.5 Visual Identity & Brand Assets

Partners are encouraged to respect visual consistency in their communications. The NPower visual identity includes:

Logo (main + inverse + icon)

Typography: New Science (titles), Kantumruy Pro (body text)

Colour Palette: Tide Blue, Jade Green, Sky Blue + two accents

Icon sets: To explain nutrient flows visually

4.6 Communication Toolkit

To support consistency and efficiency, a complete Communication Toolkit has been provided, hosted in a sharepoint folder. Partners are encouraged to consult and use these tools to ensure message alignment and efficient reporting.

It includes:

- **Templates:**
 - NPower Presentations Template
 - Deliverable Template
 - Text Documents Template
 - Dissemination and Communication Activities Report Template
 - Practice Abstracts Template (EIP Common Format)
- **Visual Identity:**
 - Logo Kit
 - Partners' Logos
 - Icon Set
 - One-Pager (A5 double-sided) (ENG/ES)
 - Roll-Up
 - Social Media Templates
 - Environmental Pictures
 - Zoom Background
 - Watermark
 - Sticker (A4)
- **Guides:**
 - Visual Identity Guidelines: Provides clear instructions on how to use the project's visual elements — including logos, fonts, and colour palette — to ensure brand consistency across all materials and partner outputs.
 - Communication Toolkit: A practical and comprehensive guide that supports partners in effectively communicating the project. It includes a project overview, partner bios for outreach, social media usage tips, useful links, and step-by-step instructions for reporting communication and dissemination activities.
- **Contact list:**
 - A spreadsheet located in the project shared folder that contains a complete list with the consortium members, including full names, roles and email contacts of people who response on behalf of every organisation.

5. Dissemination

5.1 Dissemination Strategy

The dissemination strategy of NPower aims to ensure that the project's scientific, technical, and policy-related results are not only made publicly available but actively taken up by those who can apply them. Dissemination efforts are oriented towards creating long-term value by promoting replication, scaling, and policy alignment.

To achieve this, NPower follows a stakeholder-driven and result-oriented approach, grounded in four strategic principles:

- **Timeliness** – Align dissemination with the project's development timeline to deliver relevant outputs as they mature.
- **Accessibility** – Translate complex findings into formats and language tailored to different stakeholder needs (e.g. practitioners, policy makers).
- **Credibility** – Ensure all outputs are grounded in scientific rigour and stakeholder - co-validation, increasing trust and usability.
- **Embeddedness** – Leverage existing networks within each Regional Cluster to root dissemination in local contexts, increasing potential for uptake.

Dissemination activities will be co-developed and implemented with key partners as pilot results become available. Content will include scientific publications, policy briefs, and presence at major technical and scientific events.

NPower dissemination efforts will build synergies with EU platforms and projects to broaden reach, while remaining flexible to adapt to evolving opportunities and stakeholder needs.

Given the early phase of the project, specific responsibilities for each dissemination activity are not yet assigned. These will be defined as pilots advance and outputs become demonstrable. Expected contributors include technology developers, scientific partners, governance leads, and Regional Cluster teams.

5.2 Dissemination Goals

The main objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Facilitate the uptake and application of project results across five key emitting sectors.
- Ensure visibility and accessibility of outputs through targeted formats and channels.

- Promote knowledge transfer and replication within and beyond the Regional Clusters.
- Contribute to EU policy agendas by supporting informed decision-making with robust evidence.
- Strengthen connections between science, policy, and practice through continuous stakeholder engagement.

5.3 Roles and Responsibilities

The success of dissemination activities in the NPower project depends on the active participation of all partners in the consortium. While Rural Loop leads Work Package 7 and coordinates overall communication and dissemination efforts, each partner has a responsibility to support outreach in their area of expertise and geographic scope.

The main responsibilities of consortium partners can be grouped in the following list:

- Using NPower materials and templates: The consortium has been provided with different templates and communication materials in line with NPower’s visual identity. Importantly, NPower’s and the EU’s logo with the claim “This research was funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101181873 (balancing Nitrogen and Phosphorus fLOWs by budgEting at Regional scale, NPOWER).” must be embedded in all DEC material, including the scientific publications.
- Communication on partner’s social media profiles and other owned channels: All consortium partners are encouraged to publish about their contributions to their project on their own social media accounts and to tag or mention NPower to facilitate its sharing. It is encouraged to host a brief description of NPower’s goals and objectives on the website of every beneficiary, so that eventual press releases and other DEC activities done in the beneficiary’s own language could have a source of information users can be directed to.
- Contributing to reporting: Rural Loop will compile a communication report every six months starting from October 2025 (M10). Consortium members are responsible for reporting their actions to the leader of this activity.

5.4 Dissemination actions

Scientific Publications

Peer-reviewed scientific articles will ensure the dissemination of NPower's findings to the academic and technical communities. Publications will address topics such as nutrient flow modelling, pilot results from N/P recovery technologies, life cycle and socio-economic impact assessments, and governance models developed through stakeholder co-creation.

Publications will follow the Horizon Europe open access policy and will be supported by complementary media content such as blog articles to expand reach beyond academic audiences.

Target audience: Researchers, academic institutions, scientific platforms, and policy analysts.

Participation in Scientific and Industry Events

Participation in major European science and industry fairs is a cornerstone of NPower's dissemination activities. These events offer direct opportunities to present technical progress, exchange knowledge, and establish connections with potential adopters and multipliers.

Partners will contribute through different formats such as oral presentations, posters, thematic panels, or demo materials. Content will focus on technologies, pilot actions, and governance innovations, strengthening NPower's visibility and credibility across sectors.

Expected formats: posters and roll-up banners, oral contributions in panels and conferences, demonstration videos and printed materials.

Target audience: Technical experts, researchers, policy makers, innovation clusters, and sectoral representatives.

Guidelines on Innovative Governance Measures

A set of concise, actionable guidelines will be produced and delivered to EU, national, regional, and municipal authorities. These materials aim to promote horizontal and multi-level governance approaches based on the insights and tools developed within NPower. They will support public administrations in designing and adapting policies for integrated nutrient management.

Target audience: Public administrations and policymakers at EU, national, regional and municipal levels; governance specialists and advisors.

Expected formats: digital PDF, policy briefs, downloadable factsheets.

Capacity Building Workshops

NPower will organise a series of capacity-building workshops aimed primarily at public administrations. These sessions will offer practical training on how to implement the project's innovative governance measures. In parallel, additional workshops will be conducted — potentially online — to disseminate best management practices (BMPs) to practitioners. These sessions will be tailored to specific audiences at cluster, regional, or sectoral level to ensure optimal impact and accessibility.

Target audience: Local and regional authorities; practitioners; technical advisors; stakeholder organisations in the Regional Clusters.

Expected formats: Onsite workshops, webinars, interactive sessions, recorded modules.

Policy Recommendations

A set of policy recommendations will be developed and shared online to support strategic efforts in reducing N/P pollution. These recommendations will synthesise the project's outcomes into practical guidance for policy-making and will be presented at NPower's final policy event in Brussels.

Target audience: European institutions (e.g. European Commission, European Parliament, Committee of the Regions), local government networks (e.g. Covenant of Mayors), and policymakers engaged in climate, agriculture, and environment.

Expected formats: Policy briefs, digital reports, summary presentations.

Networking Actions

To strengthen synergies and increase impact, NPower will engage in structured networking activities with other EU-funded initiatives and platforms. Key partners include the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), and Horizon Europe Missions such as *Restore our Ocean and Waters* and *A Soil Deal for Europe*.

Target audience: Sister projects, CCRI partners, EU research and innovation networks, and cross-sectoral stakeholders.

Expected formats: Bilateral meetings, joint webinars, collaborative communications and event participation.

Final Event

At the end of the project, NPower will host a final dissemination event to present its key results, policy insights, and success stories to a wide audience. The event will include interactive formats and high-level participation, fostering dialogue across science, policy, and practice.

Target audience: Broad — including project partners, EU institutions, national and local policymakers, researchers, practitioners, and media.

Expected formats: Hybrid public event with keynote talks, panel discussions, visual showcases, and networking sessions.

5.5 Synergies with Initiatives and Platforms

Clustering activities are a strategic component of Horizon Europe projects, designed to maximise impact, foster collaboration, and promote policy coherence across initiatives addressing similar societal challenges. By connecting with other EU-funded projects, clustering strengthens knowledge sharing, builds synergies, and accelerates the uptake of innovative solutions. It also supports engagement with policymakers and end-users, ensuring that research outcomes are relevant, scalable, and aligned with European priorities such as the Green Deal and the Zero Pollution Action Plan.

These activities create bridges between different sectors and levels of innovation—from research to demonstration to policy—while amplifying the visibility and reach of project results. They also provide a space for projects to co-create narratives, exchange good practices, and align their contributions with broader EU missions and partnerships.

For NPower, dedicated to reducing Nitrogen (N) and Phosphorus (P) emissions into the environment through circular, cross-sectoral approaches, clustering is fundamental to connect with a wide community working on nutrient management, sustainable agriculture, wastewater treatment, urban systems, and ecosystem restoration. These interactions enable NPower to position its technological and governance innovations within a broader policy and innovation landscape, reinforcing their applicability and long-term value.

As defined in Task 7.5 – Synergies with relevant initiatives and platforms, NPower will engage with European clusters such as the ZeroPollution4Water Cluster (with the prospect of becoming a member), which brings together water-related Horizon Europe projects addressing zero pollution. It will also collaborate with partnerships such as Water4All, through the Water-Oriented Living Labs actions, and platforms like the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), among others. Coordinated by Water Europe and with contributions from all partners, this task will support participation in joint events, co-development of policy messages, and active involvement in cross-project dialogues.

A central activity in this clustering strategy is NPower's participation in Water Projects Europe (WPE), one of the flagship formats organised by Water Europe.

WPE events cluster water-related projects to promote collaboration, mutual learning, and experience sharing on converging themes. These events aim to foster collaborative dialogue between projects, market outreach, extract policy-relevant insights, and formulate EU-level recommendations based on project results. With a pan-European scope, WPE represents a strategic communication and dissemination opportunity for NPower to showcase its solutions, connect with sister projects such as GREENHOOD and AQUAPHOENIX, and engage with other relevant initiatives funded by EU programmes, including Horizon Europe, LIFE, and INTERREG, while contributing to EU water-related policy development.

Clustering activities can be organised in conjunction with high-visibility European events to maximise outreach and audience engagement. Examples include the EU Green Week, Water Innovation Europe (WIE), and Water Knowledge Europe (WKE), as well as other relevant EU-wide initiatives or conferences. Aligning NPower's presence with these established platforms will not only amplify project visibility but also provide strategic opportunities to connect with broader stakeholder communities, including policymakers, industry, civil society, and the research and innovation ecosystem. These synergies will be explored throughout the project and integrated into the clustering calendar where relevant.

Synergies with Sister Projects

As mentioned above, NPower will be actively collaborating with sister projects AQUAPHOENIX and GREENHOOD to enhance dissemination efforts and policy relevance. These joint activities include:

- Shared social media content
- Coordinated participation in key events and EU platforms
- Co-hosted webinars and workshops

These collaborations amplify the reach of all three projects and contribute to a stronger, unified voice for circular nutrient solutions at the European level.

About the sister projects:

- AQUAPHOENIX develops large-scale technologies to recover aquaculture waste, turning it into energy, fertilisers, and sustainable feed ingredients.
- GREENHOOD focuses on regional nutrient circularity and aims to reduce nutrient losses by 50% through governance measures and sustainable practices.

5.6 Monitoring of Dissemination Actions

Throughout the project, a set of key indicators will be regularly monitored to ensure that the consortium remains responsive to emerging needs and maximises the impact of its communication and dissemination efforts. The following table outlines the main expected outcomes regarding dissemination actions, which will be reviewed on M22, M36, and M48.

Table 3. KPIs for Dissemination Actions

Action Type	Format	Target	M22	M36	M48
Scientific publications	Digital, Print	12 publications			
Attendance to scientific/industry events	Online + Onsite	40 events attended			
Guidelines on innovative governance	Digital (PDF/Briefs)	50 policymakers reached			
Capacity building workshops	Onsite	40 participants			
Policy recommendations	Digital + Onsite Event	50 policymakers reached			
Networking actions with EU initiatives	Mixed (hybrid)	15 networking actions			
Final event	Onsite	150 participants			

5.7 Partners activity reporting protocol

Reporting communication and dissemination activities is critical to ensuring both the visibility of the NPower project and compliance with European Commission requirements. Proper documentation helps us demonstrate the impact of our work, maximise outreach, and fulfil mandatory reporting obligations. All partners are expected to report their activities using the official “NPower Dissemination and Communication activities report template” (see **Annex I - Dissemination and Communication activities report template**) provided by Rural Loop.

Before the event:

Partner will send an email to fernando@rural-loop.org providing the following information:

- Partner name
- Participant(s)
- Type and name of event
- Dates
- Communication objective

During the event (suggested best practices):

When possible, partners will take at least 5 photos showing participants, a group photo, the event context, and any booth or project presentation.

- If feasible, partners will capture short videos (≥ 10 seconds). If they have previous experience, dynamic shots like panning or tracking are welcome. If not, fixed/static shots are encouraged.
- Partners will be welcomed to bring and distribute the official NPower A5 One-Pager available in the Communication Toolkit provided, which summarises the project's key goals and outcomes.

After the event:

Report the activity by submitting the “NPower Dissemination and Communication activities report template”

6. Exploitation

6.1 Exploitation objectives

Overview

In the context of this project, and as defined in the Grant Agreement, “exploitation” refers to using project outputs for additional research, innovation, or commercial purposes that extend beyond the scope of NPower.

Grant Agreement – Annex 5

Exploit(ation) — The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

As the Grant Agreement stipulates, partners are required to exploit or facilitate the exploitation of their results by other stakeholders.

Grant Agreement – Annex 5

Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must — up to four years after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1) — use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing. If, despite a beneficiary’s best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results.

Beyond this contractual obligation, the exploitation of results is crucial for maximizing the reach and impact of developed outputs, enabling them to benefit society, the economy, and the planet [1]. Within the NPower project, effective exploitation will ensure that the developed technologies, recovered fertilisers, best management practices, and innovative governance measures significantly contribute to limiting N/P emissions and re-balancing regional flows.

Two tasks are particularly dedicated to the exploitation: Task 7.3 (*EU potential for replicating circularity*) and Task 7.4 (*Exploitation strategy*). As illustrated in Figure 9, they will lead to the creation of two deliverables and the achievement of one milestone, that are presented in the following sections.

Figure 9. Overview of exploitation tasks' time frame

Months	1-6	7-12	13-18	19-24	25-30	31-36	37-42	43-48
Task 7.3							D	
Task 7.4								D M

Task active
D Deliverable
M Milestone

Task 7.3 EU potential for replicating circularity

This task will take place in the second half of the project, since it will build on results obtained in other work packages. It will be led by STRANE and supported by all other participants.

It aims to ensure the replicability and continuity of NPower's results by identifying European hotspots where its outputs can be applied. In particular, it will involve mapping key N/P sectors in Europe, analysing the availability of N/P sources, and identifying opportunities for their circular exploitation. In this task, the fertiliser market, raw material availability, and industrial symbiosis potential will also be studied.

These results will be presented in deliverable D7.9 (*Exploitation of NPower results – market access and implementation hotspots*), due in month 42. They will support the development of a coherent exploitation strategy.

Task 7.4 Exploitation strategy

Throughout the project, this comprehensive task will be undertaken to develop a structured exploitation strategy, with STRANE taking the lead and all other participants providing support. The foundational concept to define such a strategy will be that of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), as defined by the European Commission.

EU Funding & Tenders Portal [2]

A result is defined as “Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”.

A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

The primary objectives of this task are to define an exploitation strategy for the most promising KERs and to ensure that intellectual property is properly managed.

This will involve regularly compiling the status of NPower developments and the exploitation expectations of partners, as well as monitoring the emergence of new KERs. Any changes will be incorporated into updates of the DEC plan: D7.3 (*Updated DEC Plan I*) at month 22, D7.4 (*Updated DEC Plan II*) at month 36, and D7.5 (*Post-project DEC continuity Plan*) at month 48.

Each KER will be assessed to select the most promising ones. For these selected KERs, the exploitation strategy will then be refined, and efforts will be made to ensure that they meet market requirements. Suitable circular business models will be developed to accelerate commercialisation and/or replication, and business plans will be formulated.

The findings of this process will be presented in deliverable D7.10 (*Exploitation of NPower results – business plans and exploitation strategy*) due in month 47. Upon submission of this report, along with the other exploitation deliverables (D7.5: *Post-project DEC continuity plan*; D7.9: *Exploitation of NPower results – market access and implementation hotspots*), milestone 12 will be achieved.

6.2 Exploitation methodology

Phases

The methodology for developing the exploitation strategy is inspired by the EXPLOITT¹ methodology for industrial exploitation strategies. It consists of two key phases: Phase A for all KERs and Phase B, which will be performed only for the selected KERs.

Phase A will lead to the selection of the most promising KERs, with two complementary steps:

- A1 – KERs assessment: analysing the innovativeness, exploitability, and impact of each KER.
- A2 – KERs prioritisation: designing and applying a prioritisation strategy to select the most promising KERs based on the assessment from A1.

¹ The EXPLOITT methodology is a structured process developed to ensure the industrial exploitation and take-up of results generated in European projects. It was developed under the FOCUS project (Contract No: H2020 FoF-7-2014 – 637090) and is outlined in deliverable D2.2 "Methodology for industrial exploitation & take-up". In particular, it includes a "Technology assessment" stage to identify and prioritise KERs, a "Technology evaluation" stage to analyse selected KERs more in depth, and a "Business plan" stage to develop a preliminary business model for the most promising KERs. Further information on the methodology can be found in [3].

Phase B will then lead to the design of exploitation strategies for the selected KERs, with two interrelated steps:

- B1 – Detailed assessment, refinement of the exploitation strategy: conducting a deeper analysis of the selected KERs. As more information becomes available, refining the exploitation approach with KER owners, including post-project exploitation plans, ownership structure, and key barriers that may hinder market penetration.
- B2 – Designing business plans, meeting market requirements: conducting a pre-assessment of the market potential and analysing the competitive landscape. Insights from Task 7.3 (*EU potential for replicating circularity*) will then be leveraged to develop circular business models and accelerate their commercialisation and/or replication.

Figure 10 illustrates the indicative time frame for these activities. It should be noted that this timeline could be adjusted if results from other work packages are needed to make more informed decisions. Any potential changes will be indicated in DEC plan updates (deliverables D7.3, D7.4, and D7.5).

Figure 10. Time frame of the exploitation methodology

As the project advances and more information becomes available, these phases and steps will be defined more precisely, accounting for NPower's specificities. Nonetheless, at the time of submission of this Deliverable (June 2025) step A1 has already been started, and the key components that will be included are already established. They are presented in the following section.

A1: KERs assessment

Key categories for evaluating the KERs were identified through a combination of the EXPLOITT methodology, lessons learned from previous projects, and the specific context of NPower. Figure 11 illustrates how these categories are interconnected and support the selection of KERs whose innovativeness can be leveraged to create an economically viable product/service/other with positive sustainable impacts. Each of these categories is briefly described below.

Figure 11. Categories of interest and linkages for KERs assessment

Technology, concept

Most of the KERs represent technologies to recover nitrogen or phosphorus. The objective is thus to identify the key steps, inputs, outputs, main nitrogen/phosphorus flows, and the initial and final technology readiness levels (TRLs).

The TRL measures the maturity of a technology. Figure 12 presents the scale and criteria used in the context of Horizon Europe projects.

In the case of non-technological KERs, the concept, key components, and elements specific to the nature of the KER will be described.

Figure 12. TRL scale (Source: adapted from from [4])

1	Basic principles observed	Scientific research has just started, and the first results are used to be translated into future research and development.
2	Technology concept formulated	Basic principles have been studied, and first experiments/tests are designed based on the initial findings. TRL 2 technology is still very speculative.
3	Experimental proof of concept	When results from experiments/tests support the initial idea, the technology is considered to be at TRL 3. Generally, both analytical and laboratory studies are required at this level to see if a technology is ready to go to the development phases. At TRL 3, a proof-of-concept model is constructed. Reaching this point, one can conclude that the new technology is <u>feasible</u> from a <u>scientific</u> point of view.
4	Technology validated in lab	The validation of the technology has been performed at the laboratory level, testing each component so at this point a laboratory prototype is available.
5	Technology validated in relevant environment	TRL 5 is a continuation of TRL 4, but the testing environment become as closer as possible to a realistic one, although the environment is still under a control mode. Reaching this point, one can conclude that the new technology is <u>feasible</u> from a <u>technological</u> point of view.
6	Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment	For TRL 6, the prototype has to be demonstrated in a real environment, so to confirm the engineering is feasible.
7	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment	At TRL 7 the technology requires that the working model or the prototype developed to be demonstrated in an operational environment, typically under industrial conditions and timings. Reaching this point, one can conclude that the new technology is <u>reliable</u> from the <u>technological</u> point of view.
8	System complete and qualified	In TRL 8 technology is ready for implementation into an already existing technology or technology system.
9	Actual system proven in an operational environment	Once the technology system has been proven during operations, it can be called TRL 9 and considered a commercial technology.

Innovativeness

Building on the technology assessment, the innovativeness of each KER will be evaluated. This will involve identifying the key innovative features – such as steps, components, or unique combinations – that contribute to its novelty.

To contextualise these elements, they will be compared, where relevant, with existing solutions or approaches considered representative of the state-of-the-art and known competitors. At this stage, the aim is to evaluate how the KER stands out from existing concepts, without requiring an exhaustive competitor analysis.

Intellectual property rights

Once innovative elements have been identified, it is important to define the resulting intellectual property (IP) and consider the associated potential intellectual property rights (IPR). These two complementary concepts can be defined as follows.

European Commission IP Helpdesk – IP Glossary [5]

Intellectual Property (IP) refers to the creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) are private legal rights that protect the creation of the human mind: inventions, literary and artistic works, and symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce. They are

commonly divided into two categories: Industrial Property Rights (e.g. patents, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications) and Copyright and Related rights (e.g. rights of the authors/creators and those of performing artists in their performances, producers of phonograms in their recordings, and those of broadcasters in their radio and television programmes).

In particular, for each KER, the following aspects will be considered:

- Background knowledge held by project partners before the NPower project begins, and necessary to exploit the KER, as described in the Grant Agreement.

Grant Agreement – Article 16

‘Background’ means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and
- (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

- Foreground knowledge, representing results generated as part of NPower.

European Commission IP Helpdesk – IP Glossary [5]

Foreground means [...] the tangible and intangible results which are generated within a given project, including pieces of information, materials and knowledge and whether or not they can be protected.

- Ownership structure: as mentioned in the Grant Agreement, such foreground results are owned by the partners generating them. In case of joint development, the ownership structure should, however, be defined, and agreements may need to be signed.

Grant Agreement – Annex 5

Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them.

However, two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if:

- they have jointly generated them and
- it is not possible to:
 - establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or
 - separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.

The joint owners must agree — in writing — on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (‘joint ownership agreement’), to ensure compliance with their obligations under this Agreement.

- Envisaged IP protection strategy: partners will be asked how they plan to protect the innovative elements of the KER, through mechanisms such as patents, utility models, copyrights, trademarks, or trade secrets.
- Freedom-to operate (FTO): a basic FTO analysis could be conducted to determine whether the KER can be used or commercialised without infringing on existing intellectual property rights.

Market for commercial exploitation

To identify the KERs with the greatest potential for commercial exploitation, a preliminary overview will be considered for each KER, including:

- Key customers or final users, and how the KER addresses their needs.
- Size and key characteristics of the target market, including willingness-to-pay and competitors.
- Potential acceptance issues, regulatory requirements, or other barriers.

Exploitation capabilities

Once a relevant market is defined for commercial exploitation, the capabilities of the partners to exploit this market opportunity will be evaluated. In particular, the following aspects will be considered:

- Partner commitment and availability of internal resources for exploitation activities.
- Envisaged exploitation strategies and preliminary business model concepts.
- Projected time and cost required to reach the market, and expected exploitation costs.

Sustainability impacts

Finally, to facilitate the selection of KERs offering substantial sustainability benefits and minimizing negative impacts, each KER will be assessed based on:

- Expected impacts on nitrogen/phosphorus flows, quantified where feasible and described qualitatively otherwise.
- Potential other sustainability benefits.
- Compliance with the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principles of the EU Sustainable Taxonomy [6].

6.3 Key Exploitable Results overview

Nine KERs were initially identified in the Grant Agreement and are still recognised as such. Most of them represent technologies producing recovered fertilisers (RF) but other outputs were also considered as having significant potential for exploitation. Each KER is briefly presented below, combining the information

initially presented in the Grant Agreement with preliminary insights gathered through exchanges with KER owners.

Table 4. KER 1

KER 1: Biogas/fertilisers production		
Description		
Task 3.1	M1 – M24	Leader: LMB Other partners: JISAP, DAB
<p>Output: demonstrator line combining anaerobic digestion, nitrification, and composting to produce biogas and recovered fertilisers (solid and liquid) from manure and animal by-products from pig farms, as well as agricultural residues (e.g., straw, pruning waste).</p>		
Technology		
<pre> graph TD PM[Pig manure] --> S[Separation] S -- Liquid fraction --> N[Nitrification] S -- Solid fraction --> AD[Anaerobic Digestion] ABP[Animal by-products] --> AD N --> RF1((RF1)) RF1 --- DLF1[Digestate-based liquid fertiliser] AD -- Digestate liquid fraction --> RF1 AD -- Digestate solid fraction --> C[Composting] AR[Agricultural residues] --> C C --> G[Granulation] G --> RF2((RF2)) RF2 --- DLSF[Digestate-based solid fertiliser (granules)] </pre>		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: trade secret, trademark		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by LMB		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers, transport & energy industries		

Table 5. KER 2

KER 2: Bacteria cocktails and nanobubbles		
Description		
Task 3.2	M1 – M24	Leader: JISAP Other partners: LMB, DAB
<p>Output: tailored bacteria cocktails for pig manure treatment and nanobubble technology for upgrading the liquid fraction of treated/untreated manure. They aim to improve manure management and enhancing fertiliser value.</p>		
Technology		
<pre> graph TD PM([Pig manure]) --> BT[Bacteria treatment] PM --> S1[Separation] BT --> S2[Separation] S2 --> RF3((RF3)) S2 --> CLF[Conditioning + nanobubbles] RF3 --- BTF[Bacteria-treated pig manure solid fraction] CLF --- RF4((RF4)) RF4 --- BNLF[Bacteria- and nanobubble-treated pig manure liquid fraction] S1 --> ULF[Conditioning + nanobubbles] S1 --> USF[Untreated solid fraction] ULF --> RF5((RF5)) RF5 --- NTLF[Nanobubble-treated pig manure liquid fraction] USF --- PJKER1[Possibility to join KER 1] </pre>		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: trade secret, trademark, licensing		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by DAB		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers		

Table 6. KER 3

KER 3: Recovery of N/P fertilisers green filters		
Description		
Task 3.3	M1 – M24	Leader: IMIDA
<p>Output: demonstrator line incorporating constructed wetlands for the production of Salicornia – a halophyte plant with high value in the food and cosmetic industries – from nitrogen/phosphorus-rich fish production effluent. After effluent settling, Salicornia plants in the constructed wetlands will uptake nitrogen/phosphorus and incorporate it to their tissues, producing clean seawater to be discharged in the sea.</p>		
Technology		
<pre> graph LR A([Fish production effluent]) --> B[Effluent settling tank] B --> C[Salicornia constructed wetlands] C -- Recycled water --> D[Marine environment] C --> E[Salicornia harvesting] E --> F((S)) F --- G[Salicornia biomass] </pre>		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: utility model		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by IMIDA		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers		

Table 7. KER 4

KER 4: Recovery of phosphate salts from urban wastewater		
Description		
Task 3.4	M1 – M24	Leader: CTQ Other partners: HGA
<p>Output: demonstrator of a technological solution to produce a range of phosphate salts from urban wastewater using an innovative combination of steps.</p>		
Technology		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: utility model		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by CTQ/HGA		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers		

Table 8. KER 5

KER 5: Recovery of N-rich reclaimed water from urban wastewater		
Description		
Task 3.5	M1 – M24	Leader: CTQ Other partners: HGA
<p>Output: demonstrator of an innovative process to reclaim nitrogen-rich water for fertigation from urban wastewater. The process combines several technologies to guarantee the fertiliser value and safety of the reclaimed water.</p>		
Technology		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: utility model		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by CTQ/HGA		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers		

Table 9. KER 6

KER 6: Recycling of run-off water for irrigation		
Description		
Task 3.6	M1 – M24	Leader: CETENMA Other partners: CSIC
<p>Output: demonstrator of a technological solution to remove nitrogen from contaminated brackish streams, highly polluted with nitrogen as a result of run-off from agriculture and other sectors. The reclaimed water will be supplemented with key micronutrients and leveraged as irrigation water with negligible nitrogen concentration.</p>		
Technology		
<pre> graph LR A([N-polluted stream]) --> B[Pre-treatment (sand filter, microfiltration, disinfection)] B --> C[Nanofiltration (membranes)] C -- Permeate --> D[Aeration] C -- Retentate --> E[WWTP] D --> F[Biological denitrification (SBR reactor)] G[Carbon source (Sodium/potassium acetate, agrifood industry byproducts)] --> F F --> H[Conditioning (sieving, microfiltration, UV disinfection)] I[Micronutrients (Fe, Mn...)] --> H H --> J((RF8)) J --- K[Low-N water with micronutrients] </pre>		
Initial TRL and expected final TRL: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: know-how-licensing		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by CETENMA		
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers		

Table 10. KER 7

KER 7: 8 recovered fertilisers (RF1-RF8)			
Description			
Task 3.7	M16 – M33	Leader: PBT	Other partners: CETENMA, CTQ, HGA, IMIDA, LMB, JISAP, DAB, CSIC
Task 3.8	M19 – M42	Leader: CSIC	Other partners: CETENMA, CTQ, HGA, IMIDA, LMB, JISAP, DAB, FECOAM, PBT
Output: 8 recovered fertilisers (RF1-RF8) produced as outputs of technologies T1-T6 (KERs 1-6)			
Intellectual Property and Exploitation			
Envisaged protection: trade secret, trademark			
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation the partners developing each corresponding technology: LMB (T1), JISAP (T2), IMIDA (T3), CTQ (T4, T5), CETENMA (T6) and by PBT (QA T1-T6).			
Envisaged target clients: agrochemical producers, farmers			

Table 11. KER 8

KER 8: Dynamic software for N/P budgeting			
Description			
Task 2.1	M1 – M15	Leader: UGENT	Other partners: CETENMA, CTQ, HGA, CSIC, IMIDA, LUKE, UPCT, MTU, UCD, LMB, JISAP, DAB, PBT, FMRM, FECOAM, BOER, IBF, MTK, CARM
Task 2.2	M16 – M40	Leader: UGENT	Other partners: CETENMA
Output: nitrogen/phosphorus budgeting software model for the Spanish region of Murcia, that will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● consider N/P inputs and outputs from key N/P emitting sectors ● establish a maximum allowable input of N/P in the region ● evaluate the impacts of environmental, economic and behavioural changes such as those promoted by NPower 			
Intellectual Property and Exploitation			
Envisaged protection: know-how, licensing			
Envisaged exploitation strategy: direct exploitation by UGENT and licensed use of the software			
Envisaged target clients: research centres, public bodies, fertiliser companies			

Table 12. KER 9

KER 9: Series of workshops on N/P limiting		
Description		
Task 5.2	M24 – M48	Leader: FMRM Other partners: CETENMA, UGENT, MTU, LUKE, UCD, WE, CARM
Output: workshops for policy representatives to learn about NPower’s innovative governance measures and how to implement them.		
Intellectual Property and Exploitation		
Envisaged protection: know-how		
Envisaged exploitation strategy: online platform of webinars for policy makers, advisory services for 45 municipalities in the region of Murcia		
Envisaged target clients: municipalities		

6.4 Intellectual Property management strategy

Overview

While IP management is partially addressed within the exploitation methodology, not all developed IP will be prioritised for exploitation. It is thus essential to consider a separate IP management strategy that will complement the exploitation strategy – even though some overlap may occur for selected KERs.

Indeed, the Grant Agreement with the European Commission mandates an appropriate protection of the IP developed within the project – where possible and justified.

Grant Agreement – Annex 5

Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results – for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage – if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests.

Such protection not only fulfils contractual obligations but also enhances the potential for future commercial use – whether by internal or external stakeholders – thus increasing the likelihood of achieving meaningful impact.

Strategy

The strategy to manage IP can be divided into general recommendations and three key parts:

- 0) Recommendations to avoid jeopardising IP
- 1) To clarify the ownership of the IP generated within the project while complying with Open Science requirements, we recommend including a copyright notice in all documents, publications, and public deliverables. Below is an example of a possible copyright notice.

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Furthermore, to avoid jeopardising potential IP protection, it is reminded that, as stipulated in the Grant Agreement, partners are required to give at least 15 days' notice before disseminating their results, allowing other consortium members to object if disclosure could compromise future IP rights.

Grant Agreement – Annex 5

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

- 2) Background

As previously defined, background refers to the intellectual property owned by project partners prior to the start of the project that is necessary to correctly implement the project. It is thus important to clarify such aspects early on to prevent potential disputes. For the NPower project, the background was outlined in the Consortium Agreement and agreed upon by all partners (see Table 10). However, we identified a discrepancy between this declaration and the one included in the Grant Agreement (CTQ's patent appears in the latter but not the former). This issue is currently being addressed.

Table 13. Background declared in the Consortium Agreement

Partner	Declared background
LMB	Lambert's knowledge that gives rise to solutions, designs and operation of pilot plants.
	The pilot plants: whether own or from Lambert collaborators, with their necessary annexes and software
	The operations of the pilot plants, including: their protocols and operation and maintenance methods
PBT	Know-how concerning the utilization, application, selection of microorganisms, active substances and organic molecules that have biofertilizing and biostimulant effects.
	Know-how concerning the adaptation of microorganisms, active substances and organic molecules to the carriers developed in this Project.
	PROBELTE trademark
DAB	DAB technology uses natural bacteria in high concentrations to carry out hydrolysis of solids and accelerate the nitrification and denitrification processes in pig slurry, with the consequent reduction of ammonia and greenhouse gases. The treatment is carried out by applying a biological pool in the pits of the sheds. Quantity, frequency and composition will be determined according to the farm in order to achieve the inoculation and maintenance of the bacteria in the slurry. The pool will be prepared in each facility using a simple biogrow technique.

3) Foreground:

As previously mentioned, foreground results are those generated as part of the project. Each of the nine identified KERs is thus a foreground result (selected for its high potential for exploitation). Table 11 presents the initially identified pieces of expected intellectual property to be generated within the project. At this point, they are closely aligned with the KERs but have been reorganised and numbered to facilitate the future description of ownership structure and expected IP protection. In particular, each technology was grouped with its output recovered fertilisers (for instance technology T1 generates RF1 and RF2) since IP owners can expected to be similar and because considering them together will help define a coherent IP protection strategy. Additionally, two pieces that do not represent KERs but are still generated IP were added (IP7 and IP10).

With the help of Work Package Leaders, additional pieces of intellectual property may be identified as the project progresses. The table will also be completed to include the ownership structure. If necessary, workshops will be organised to reach agreement with other consortium members.

Table 14. Initial intellectual property table

Name	Expected intellectual property	WP
IP1	a) Technology T1: Biogas/fertilisers production from agri-food residues	3
	b) RF1: Digestate-based liquid fertiliser	
	c) RF2: Digestate-based solid fertiliser (granules)	
IP2	a) Technology T2: Bacteria cocktails and nanobubbles for pig manure treatment	3
	b) RF3: Bacteria-treated pig manure solid fraction	
	c) RF4: Bacteria- and nanobubble-treated pig manure liquid fraction	
	d) RF5: Nanobubble-treated pig manure fraction	
IP3	a) Technology T3: Halophyte production from aquaculture effluent	3
	b) Produced Salicornia biomass	
IP4	a) Technology T4: Recovery of phosphate salts from urban wastewater	3
	b) RF6: Phosphate salts	
IP5	a) Technology T5: Recovery of N-rich reclaimed water from urban wastewater	3
	b) RF7: N-rich reclaimed water	
IP6	a) Technology T6: Recycling of run-off water for irrigation	3
	b) RF8: Low-N water with micronutrients	
IP7	a) Economic, social, and environmental impact of NPower's solutions	6
IP8	a) N/P budgeting for the region of Murcia	2
IP9	a) Innovative governance measures (including a kit)	5
IP10	a) Best Management Practices (including Practice Abstracts)	4

4) Foreground protection

For each piece of IP, the owners will be asked about their plans for IP protection. For instance, they could rely on patents, utility models, copyright, trademarks, or trade secrets – if possible and relevant.

7. Conclusions

During this first six months period (M1-M6) of the NPower project, a strong foundation has been established for its dissemination, exploitation and communication efforts. A comprehensive Communication Toolkit has been delivered, including visual guidelines, templates, and reporting instructions to support consistent project outreach. The project webpage is fully operational in both English and Spanish, serving as a hub for project visibility. Core channels have been launched, including the LinkedIn page and YouTube channel, where the first batch of videos and general content have been published to introduce the project's goals. Additionally, Rural Loop and Strane Innovation have initiated bilateral meetings with partners to gain deeper insight into their roles, motivations, and contributions. This dialogue is key to crafting targeted and representative content moving forward.

The next steps will include the development of new multimedia formats, including the first podcast season and the “Explained in a Minute” video series. Furthermore, the AI assistant “Powie” will be gradually integrated into the website to enhance user engagement and provide curated, accessible information on N/P challenges and solutions as the pilots and Regional Clusters evolve.

On the exploitation side, the current phase has focused on outlining the methodology and strategy that will guide the identification and prioritization of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Initial assessments have begun, but meaningful exploitation — including the development of business models and intellectual property (IP) management plans — will depend on the technical maturation of the project's innovations. As pilot activities evolve and outputs become demonstrable, the exploitation strategy will be progressively refined to ensure that the most promising results are aligned with market opportunities and stakeholder needs.

This plan is a living document that will be revisited and updated throughout the project lifecycle, specifically on M22 and M36, plus the Post-project DEC continuity Plan to be delivered on M48. This document will adapt to reflect project progress, emerging opportunities, and partners inputs, ensuring it remains aligned with NPower's DEC goals and ambitions.

8. References

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9. Annexes

Annex I - Dissemination and Communication activities report template

Available for all Consortium members [at this URL](#).

Sección 1 de 4

NPower Dissemination and Communication activities report template

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The "NPower Dissemination and Communication activities report template" is a structured document designed to track and report the dissemination and communication activities and outreach efforts associated with the NPower project. It provides a clear format for documenting events, communications, and engagement activities, helping to ensure that the project's progress and impact are effectively shared with relevant stakeholders.

Correo *

Correo válido

Este formulario registra los correos. [Cambiar configuración](#)

Partner who undertook the action: *

Choose type of activity *

- Dissemination activity (describing and making results available for use)
- Communication activity (informing about the project and its results)
- Article or mention in media/press (newspapers, TV, radio, digital media, etc.)

Dissemination activity reporting

Descripción (opcional)

1. Title or name of the activity: *

Texto de respuesta corta

2. What? *

Type of the dissemination activity

- Clustering activities
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects
- Conferences (such as trade fairs and scientific conferences)
- Education and training events (e.g. capacity building workshops)
- Meetings
- Other (such as publications)
- Other scientific collaboration

3. Where was the event held (or "online" if appropriate): *

Texto de respuesta corta

.....

4. When was the event held: *

Mes, día, año

5. Estimated number of people attending: *

Texto de respuesta corta

.....

6. Who? *

Target audience reached

- Industry, business partners
- Innovators
- EU Institutions
- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities
- Civil Society
- Citizens
- Research communities
- Specific and end user communities
- International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc..)
- Other
- Investors

7. If "Other" was selected, please fill the text box below with the stakeholder reached:

Texto de respuesta corta

8. Brief description of the event: *

Texto de respuesta larga

9. Why? *

Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)

Texto de respuesta larga

10. Status of the dissemination activity *

- Delivered
- Ongoing
- Postponed
- Cancelled

11. Upload photos and videos recorded during the activity *

 Añadir archivo

 Ver carpeta

Communication activity reporting

Descripción (opcional)

1. Communication activity name *

Texto de respuesta corta

2. Description *

Texto de respuesta larga

3. Where was the event held (or "online" if appropriate): *

Texto de respuesta corta

4. When was the event held? *

Mes, día, año

5. Estimated number of people attending: *

Texto de respuesta corta

6. Who? *

Target audience

- Industry, business partners
- Innovators
- EU Institutions
- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities
- Civil society
- Citizens
- Research communities
- Specific and end user communities
- International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc..)

Other

Investors

7. If "Other" was selected, please fill the text box below with the stakeholder reached:

Texto de respuesta corta
.....

8. How? *

Communication channel

Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)

Exhibition

Interview

Media article

Newsletter

Other

Press release

- Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)
- Social media
- TV/Radio campaigns
- Video
- Website

9. Outcome *

Texto de respuesta larga

10. Status *

- Delivered
- Ongoing
- Postponed
- Cancelled

11. Upload photos and videos recorded during the activity *

 Añadir archivo

 Ver carpeta

Media/Press

Descripción (opcional)

Please share the link(s) along with a brief description of the reason or topic of the article or interview. *

Texto de respuesta larga
